

PEER REVIEW REPORT

Peer review report for:

De Santana Junior, J. L., Pimentel, R. C., Malacrida, M. J. C (2025). The information content of losses versus profits and the denominator effect of risk. *RAE-Revista de Administração de Empresas*, 65(5), e2023-0501. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/S0034-759020250502>

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De Santana Junior, J. L., Pimentel, R. C., Malacrida, M. J. C (2025). Peer review report for: The information content of losses versus profits and the denominator effect of risk. *RAE-Revista de Administração de Empresas*, 65(5), e2023-0501. *Zenodo*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14996407>

Disclaimer: The content of the Peer Review Report is the full copy of the reviewers' and authors' reports. Typing and punctuation errors are not edited.

Reviewers:

Jose Alves Dantas , Universidade de Brasília, Departamento de Ciências Contábeis e Atuariais, Brasília, DF, Brazil.

The second reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

Micael Jardim , Fundação Getulio Vargas, Escola Brasileira de Administração Pública e de Empresas, Rio de Janeiro, RJ, Brazil

ROUND 1

Reviewer 1 Report

Reviewer: Jose Alves Dantas

Date review returned: 23-Dec-2023

Recommendation: Major Revision

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).

none

Comments to the Author

O estudo apresenta um conjunto de aspectos que o tornam com alto potencial de publicação, destacando-se:

- Aborda tema relevante para a literatura de finanças, em especial quanto ao impacto das informações contábeis no mercado de capitais.
- O texto é objetivo, com linha argumentativa consistente e de fácil compreensão.
- A revisão de literatura é abrangente e consistente com o propósito do estudo, permitindo compreender o estágio de desenvolvimento em âmbito internacional e identificar o gap na literatura nacional.
- O rigor metodológico aplicado no desenvolvimento da pesquisa, incluindo a descrição e justificativa das variáveis que compõem os modelos estimados e a realização de testes adicionais, em relação ao conservadorismo condicional e aos ativos ocultos, entre outros.
- A análise de resultados, de forma geral, é cuidadosa e criteriosa, suportado nas evidências empíricas obtidas.
- Não obstante, há itens que merecem ser melhor explorados ou esclarecidos, no sentido de aprimorar o artigo, entre os quais se destacam:
 - a. O estudo precisa deixar mais claro o que propõe de novo para complementar o conhecimento existente. Qual o gap de pesquisa preenchido? Os autores procuram destacar as contribuições do artigo para a literatura, mas em termos da prática contábil, quais os agentes interessados no resultado da pesquisa? O que o estudo apresenta de inovador? Qual a contribuição marginal para a literatura? Qual a novidade?
 - b. Na hipótese H1 é prevista a perspectiva de que o ERC de empresas com prejuízo seria menor do que empresas com lucro. O método empregado testa, porém, se a relação entre o retorno não esperado e o resultado não esperado é menor para empresas com registro de prejuízo. É preciso deixar mais claro como a relação entre as parcelas não esperada do resultado e do retorno traduziriam exatamente a relação entre o resultado e o retorno.
 - c. Mesma questionamento se aplica à hipótese H2.
 - d. De acordo com o texto, a amostra da pesquisa alcança todas as companhias de capital aberto, de 2001 a 2021. A esse respeito, duas questões precisam ser melhor esclarecidas e discutidas. A amostra contempla entidades financeiras e não financeiras? Se sim, não seria um problema não controlar os efeitos associados à natureza das operações das instituições financeiras, em especial a alavancagem e o risco de corrida bancária em caso de prejuízos, e reflexos na composição do resultado? No período considerado há dois modelos contábeis substancialmente distintos, com a adoção dos padrões IFRS a partir de 2010. A formação do resultado das entidades pesquisadas muda substancialmente a partir da adoção do novo modelo contábil. Isso foi controlado? Sim? Não? Por quê?
 - e. No segundo parágrafo após a equação (2) é afirmado que a hipótese H1 é corroborada se o coeficiente Beta 4 for negativo. Não teria a necessidade de comparar com o coeficiente Beta 2?
 - f. Não ficou clara a razão para a escolha metodológica de utilizar retornos mensais dos últimos 48 meses para estimar o retorno previsto, na equação (4). Por que não utilizar retornos diários, que seriam mais assertivos na identificação do comportamento do retorno dos papéis em relação ao mercado? Isso evitaria, inclusive, o uso de dados dos 4 anos anteriores, evitando a perda de observações.
 - g. Na Tabela 2 senti falta dos pontos máximos e mínimos nas estatísticas descritivas, o que possibilitaria melhor compreensão por parte do leitor sobre as características dos dados. Isso é particularmente importante para se entender a razão pela aplicação da winsorização, que tem repercussão nesses valores extremos.

- h. A seção das Conclusões está parecendo mais uma seção de análise de resultados. Na verdade, na seção dos resultados tinha faltado essa reflexão sobre os efeitos e implicações econômicas dos testes empíricos. Na seção das Conclusões é o espaço dos autores, sendo de certa forma impertinente a recorrência de citações da literatura. É a oportunidade de os autores trazerem suas percepções a respeito da pesquisa, incluindo os aspectos fundamentais dos achados empíricos, as contribuições do estudo, as limitações, etc.*
- i. Embora no abstract o objetivo do estudo esteja bem claro, na Introdução o texto está relativamente confuso, sem foco muito claro.*
- j. No abstract faltou abordar os resultados dos testes em relação ao conservadorismo contábil e aos ativos ocultos.*
- k. Os autores destacam como uma das características do mercado brasileiro a adoção de programas de empréstimos/financiamentos incentivados para prover liquidez as empresas, o que pode propiciar o prolongamento do registro de perdas. Como exemplo, cita os programas emergenciais adotados no período da pandemia da Covid-19. O problema é que esses programas foram implementados pelos mais diversos governos, em especial os dos países mais desenvolvidos, para mitigar os impactos econômicos causados. Seria recomendável, portanto, encontrar exemplos que sejam diferenciais para a economia brasileira.*
- l. Na Seção Empirical Approach há a menção à Subseção 3.3, mas não há essa numeração nos tópicos do artigo.*
- m. A equação (3) parece estar incompleta. Não dá para identificar, por exemplo, o que compõe a variável de interação referente ao coeficiente Beta δ .*

Reviewer 2 Report

The reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

Authors' Responses

Dear editors and reviewers,

We appreciate the opportunity to review our article submitted to RAE - Revista de Administração de Empresas and the constructive comments of the reviewers, which, we believe, gave us the possibility to make substantial improvements in the work. We made several changes according to indications, suggestions and requests. We proceeded to respond to the comments of the reviewers in all aspects.

- 1. The abstract could benefit from clearer language and stronger emphasis on the findings. The results demonstrate that “risk influences how earnings from companies reporting losses and profits are perceived,” showing that losses are less informative than profits for low- and medium-risk firms, while this difference disappears for high-risk firms. Phrases like “information content of losses” could be replaced with “companies reporting losses,” and “earnings informativeness” with “how earnings explain a company’s value” to enhance clarity. Simplifying terms such as “liquidation value” to “the value of a company’s assets if it shuts down” and briefly defining “Earnings Response Coefficient (ERC)” as “how strongly stock prices respond to earnings” would make the text more accessible.*

We appreciate your valuable suggestions. Following your feedback, we have revised the text accordingly to address your points.

2. *While controlled regression may not establish causality definitively, the methodology should be designed to approach it logically and rigorously. Demonstrating correlation alone offers limited value, as it does not truly enhance our understanding. The paper should aim to explore cause-and-effect relationships to make a meaningful contribution to the literature and practice. The use of “dummy” for binary variables is technically imprecise and should be replaced with “binary variable” to maintain accuracy.*

Thank you for pointing this out. As per your suggestion, we have replaced the term ‘dummy’ with ‘binary’ throughout the manuscript. We completely agree that establishing causal relationships, even in the absence of definitive proof, is a critical goal for impactful research. In our study, we sought to approach causality rigorously within the methodological constraints and standards established in the relevant literature. The research design we adopted is consistent with prior studies, where causality is approached through a combination of analyses and tests that examine a specific explanation while controlling for confounding factors aligned with the theoretical framework being tested.

Additionally, since our paper introduces a novel aspect—the effect of risk—employing a methodological approach consistent with prior literature ensures that we test this specific contribution in a manner that is both robust and comparable. Adopting a drastically different methodological framework could shift the focus of the work and detract from its intended contribution to the literature.

We appreciate your insights and hope that this explanation clarifies the methodological choices made in the study.

3. *The abstract and the first paragraph of the introduction are critical to capturing the reader’s attention. Applying the guidance from Grant and Pollock (2011) could help make these sections more compelling. The introduction does not clearly define the research question or convincingly justify the study’s relevance. While the focus on earnings informativeness in an emerging market context is claimed to be novel, the authors fail to demonstrate how it advances existing literature. The relationship between risk, liquidation options, and earnings informativeness is not well-defined and could be framed more effectively. The third paragraph of the introduction illustrates broader issues with coherence and focus. It starts by addressing the valuation challenges of loss-making firms but quickly shifts to unrelated topics like shareholder value destruction, bankruptcy costs, and protectionist policies, without clearly connecting these ideas. The phrase “especially in countries where poverty and inequality are significant, such as the case of the Brazilian economy” conflates countries with economies and introduces Brazil in an unclear context. The assumption that all loss-making firms destroy value is problematic, as it ignores scenarios where losses result from productive investments or growth strategies. This disorganized approach weakens the argument.*

Thank you for your detailed feedback on the introduction. We greatly appreciate your comments and structure suggestions, which have helped us refine the structure and coherence of the manuscript. In line with Grant and Pollock (2011), we tried to make explicit in the introduction “who cares” with the topic and findings.

In response to your observations:

- *The third paragraph has been relocated to a more suitable section of the text, where it now serves as an introduction to the context of firms reporting losses. This placement provides a clearer connection to the discussion and avoids diluting the focus of the introduction.*
- *We have removed the statement about value destruction. Our intention was not to assume that all loss-making firms destroy value but rather to emphasize that, under certain circumstances discussed in the cited literature, losses can perpetuate and lead to adverse outcomes. This nuance is better presented in its new location within the manuscript.*

- Regarding the association between losses and growth strategies, we acknowledge the importance of this perspective, which is explicitly considered in our work. Our additional tests (hidden assets analysis) aim to indirectly address this matter.

We hope these revisions address your concerns and strengthen the clarity and focus of the manuscript.

4. The first paragraph on page 5 discusses the relationship between risk and ERC, attributing a negative association to the “denominator effect” in a dividend-based valuation model. However, this analysis does not appear to provide significant theoretical or practical contributions. The negative relationship between risk and ERC is already established in prior literature, and while the discussion of numerator and denominator effects attempts to contextualize the findings, it does not offer a novel perspective. The claim that “ERC tends to zero” for high-risk firms could be a meaningful contribution, but it is not sufficiently developed or linked to actionable implications for investors or practitioners.

We have included a clarification that prior studies have not consistently found the denominator effect to outweigh the numerator effect. In certain contexts, this dynamic could lead to an increase, rather than a decrease, in the ERC difference between loss-making and profit-making firms. Our findings advance the literature by providing evidence in support of the conditions under which the denominator effect prevails, thus contributing to a deeper understanding of these dynamics.

We hope this addition addresses your concerns and provides clearer justification for the contribution of our study.

5. The phrase “liquidation/abandonment” reflects poor writing and should be replaced with precise terms like “liquidation or abandonment” to improve readability and professionalism. Furthermore, the analyses of conditional conservatism and hidden assets highlight weaknesses in the paper’s overall contribution. Using Basu’s (1997) model to test conditional conservatism does not provide novel insights, as the findings align with existing literature. Similarly, proxies for hidden assets, such as “listing age” and “industry,” are overly simplistic and fail to capture the complexity of intangible or underreported assets. The reliance on process-of-elimination reasoning to conclude that the “liquidation or abandonment option” is the primary explanation weakens the argument, as it lacks strong direct evidence.

Thank you for your valuable feedback. We have made the suggested revision and replaced the term “liquidation/abandonment” with “liquidation or abandonment” to improve clarity.

Regarding the issues you raised about the analyses of conditional conservatism and hidden assets, we would like to clarify the purpose of these analyses in the context of our paper. The paper is not aimed at providing new evidence on conditional conservatism, which is why this analysis was conducted as an additional test without formulating specific hypotheses. The main objective of the paper is to contribute to the understanding of the informativeness of losses and the effect of risk on the informativeness of earnings.

While it is true that the conditional conservatism model aligns with previous literature, we felt it was important to consider this aspect in our study, especially in the context of Brazil, where this has not been tested before. Thus, we cannot ignore conservatism as a potential explanation for our findings. However, we acknowledge that conservatism is not the main focus of the paper, and similar to the analysis of hidden assets, it serves to strengthen the robustness of our results.

Our primary contribution lies in the “liquidation or abandonment option,” as emphasized in the introduction. We agree with your observation that both the conservatism and hidden assets analyses offer indirect tests of alternative explanations. To address this, we have incorporated these aspects as suggestions for future research.

6. Additionally, the paper must integrate the relevance of Brazil more clearly into its analysis. Why Brazil matters as the focus of the study should be explicitly articulated and tied to the paper's central arguments.

Thank you for the comment. Due to the international novelty of the approach, we believe that the purpose is not analyse the Brazilian market itself, but the economic relationship between loss reporting, accounting informativeness and risk.

Nonetheless, we expanded the explanation of the Brazilian case, as presented in the introduction and along the manuscript, the central argument for the Brazilian market relies on the fact that (1) the role of accounting information on loss firms are particularly relevant, since Brazilian official it adopts loan programs to provide liquidity to firms, which can prolong loss reporting (Acharya et al., 2019, Caballero et al., 2008, Zoller-Rydzek & Keller, 2020). (2) The Brazilian market has high levels of risk, uncertainty and governmental protectionism and low levels of financial disclosure and governance

7. The theoretical framework could benefit from further development to fully provide a strong foundation for the research. While the references to Hayn (1995) and related works are relevant, there is a missed opportunity to critically engage with this literature to better establish the paper's contribution. For example, the "denominator effect" is introduced but not sufficiently explained, leaving its theoretical significance unclear and the reader without a strong understanding of its role in the study. Expanding the theoretical framework to explicitly discuss how this work advances the understanding of earnings informativeness in high-risk contexts would strengthen the paper. Clarifying the gap in the literature and providing a more robust rationale for the hypotheses would also help the reader appreciate the study's originality.

Thank you for your feedback. We have expanded the theoretical framework to better engage with the literature on the "denominator effect" and its implications for earnings informativeness in high-risk contexts. We have clarified the theoretical significance of this concept and explicitly discussed how our study advances the understanding of earnings informativeness in firms facing high levels of risk, particularly those reporting losses. Additionally, we have highlighted the gap in the literature that our study addresses and strengthened the rationale for our hypotheses.

8. Additionally, the inclusion of analyses on conditional conservatism and hidden assets appears disconnected from the stated hypotheses. These analyses aim to explain why losses may have low informativeness, but they are not presented as hypotheses or explicitly tied to the theoretical framework. This lack of alignment creates a sense of methodological inconsistency, making it difficult for the reader to understand how these analyses fit into the overall research objectives. Better integration of these elements into the framework would enhance the coherence and focus of the paper.

Thank you for your comment. In response, we have added additional explanations to clarify the role of these supplemental analyses, while respecting the journal's word limit. These analyses are presented as important tools for ruling out alternative explanations and adding nuance to the primary phenomenon under investigation, a practice well-aligned with methodological norms in the literature.

For example, Section 5 of Hayn (1995) is devoted entirely to this type of supplemental testing without formal hypotheses, aimed at exploring alternative explanations for the primary findings. Similarly, Basu (1997) conducts additional analyses in Section 6 to test alternative interpretations of the conservatism effect. More recently, Gu et al. (2023) employ comparable approaches to enhance the robustness of their conclusions. All these papers are in the reference list of our manuscript.

While we acknowledge the limitations of these additional analyses, we believe their inclusion is critical to providing a more comprehensive understanding of the findings. We have revised the manuscript to ensure these elements are better integrated into the overall framework to address concerns about methodological coherence.

9. *I noticed that the decision to include banks was addressed in a response to a previous reviewer. However, since it is generally common practice to exclude banks, it would be important to clearly explain this choice in the paper. I appreciate the argument provided for their inclusion, as it is well-reasoned. I understand that the methodological approach has already been discussed extensively with other reviewers, and there may be little to add at this stage. That said, presenting the model more clearly in the paper would be highly beneficial. Not all readers will be highly specialized researchers, so ensuring accessibility will help broaden the paper's impact and reach.*

We provide explanation for keeping banks and also reported all the results with a sub-sample without banks in the tables as an additional result. The results are all qualitative the same with and without banks. We further provided additional information to the models for clearly.

10. *I encourage the authors to revisit the objectives of their study and provide a concise summary of their key findings and contributions. Clarifying the broader significance of the work and suggesting directions for future research would enhance its impact. A strong final paragraph should highlight the paper's relevance and leave the reader with an inspiring and forward-looking message.*

We have carefully considered your comments and made the following adjustments to better clarify the objectives, key findings, broader significance, and potential directions for future research in our conclusion.

ROUND 2

Reviewer 1 Report

Reviewer: Jose Alves Dantas

Date review returned: 22-Jun-2024

Recommendation: Accept

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).

none

Comments to the Author

As providências adotadas, os ajustes promovidos e as explicações apresentadas em relação aos questionamentos, sugestões e recomendações formuladas na primeira rodada de avaliação foram suficientemente adequadas.

No meu entendimento, o artigo está em condições de ser aceito para publicação.

Reviewer 2 Report

The second reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

Reviewer 3 Report

Reviewer: Micael Jardim

Date review returned: 25-Nov-2024

Recommendation: Major Revision

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).

none

Comments to the Author

*Thank you for allowing me to review the manuscript, *The Information Content of Losses Versus Profits and the Denominator Effect of Risk*. While the topic is relevant, the finding is not trivial and the methodology is well-documented, the writing quality, theoretical framing, clarity of objectives needs significant improvement.*

Below, I provide detailed feedback organized by section.

1. Abstract and Introduction

The abstract could benefit from clearer language and stronger emphasis on the findings. The results demonstrate that “risk influences how earnings from companies reporting losses and profits are perceived,” showing that losses are less informative than profits for low- and medium-risk firms, while this difference disappears for high-risk firms. Phrases like “information content of losses” could be replaced with “companies reporting losses,” and “earnings informativeness” with “how earnings explain a company’s value” to enhance clarity. Simplifying terms such as “liquidation value” to “the value of a company’s assets if it shuts down” and briefly defining “Earnings Response Coefficient (ERC)” as “how strongly stock prices respond to earnings” would make the text more accessible.

While controlled regression may not establish causality definitively, the methodology should be designed to approach it logically and rigorously. Demonstrating correlation alone offers limited value, as it does not truly enhance our understanding. The paper should aim to explore cause-and-effect relationships to make a meaningful contribution to the literature and practice. Additionally, the use of “dummy” for binary variables is technically imprecise and should be replaced with “binary variable” to maintain accuracy.

The abstract and the first paragraph of the introduction are critical to capturing the reader’s attention. Applying the guidance from Grant and Pollock (2011) could help make these sections more compelling. The introduction does not clearly define the research question or convincingly justify the study’s relevance. While the focus on earnings informativeness in an emerging market context is claimed to be novel, the authors fail to demonstrate how it advances existing literature. The relationship between risk, liquidation options, and earnings informativeness is not well-defined and could be framed more effectively.

The third paragraph of the introduction illustrates broader issues with coherence and focus. It starts by addressing the valuation challenges of loss-making firms but quickly shifts to unrelated topics like shareholder value destruction, bankruptcy costs, and protectionist policies, without clearly connecting these ideas. The phrase “especially in countries where poverty and inequality are significant, such as the case of the Brazilian economy” conflates countries with economies and introduces Brazil in an unclear context. The assumption that all loss-making firms destroy value is problematic, as it ignores scenarios where losses result from productive investments or growth strategies. This disorganized approach weakens the argument.

The first paragraph on page 5 discusses the relationship between risk and ERC, attributing a negative association to the “denominator effect” in a dividend-based valuation model. However, this analysis does not appear to provide significant theoretical or practical contributions. The negative relationship between risk and ERC is already established in prior literature, and while the discussion of numerator and denominator effects attempts to contextualize the findings, it does not offer a novel perspective. The claim that “ERC tends to zero” for high-risk firms could be a meaningful contribution, but it is not sufficiently developed or linked to actionable implications for investors or practitioners.

The phrase “liquidation/abandonment” reflects poor writing and should be replaced with precise terms like “liquidation or abandonment” to improve readability and professionalism. Furthermore, the analyses of conditional conservatism and hidden assets highlight weaknesses in the paper’s overall contribution. Using Basu’s (1997) model to test conditional conservatism does not provide novel insights, as the findings align with existing literature. Similarly, proxies for hidden assets, such as “listing age” and “industry,” are overly simplistic and fail to capture the complexity of intangible or underreported assets. The reliance on process-of-elimination reasoning to conclude that the “liquidation or abandonment option” is the primary explanation weakens the argument, as it lacks strong direct evidence.

Additionally, the paper must integrate the relevance of Brazil more clearly into its analysis. Why Brazil matters as the focus of the study should be explicitly articulated and tied to the paper’s central arguments.

2. Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework could benefit from further development to fully provide a strong foundation for the research. While the references to Hayn (1995) and related works are relevant, there is a missed opportunity to critically engage with this literature to better establish the paper’s contribution. For example, the “denominator effect” is introduced but not sufficiently explained, leaving its theoretical significance unclear and the reader without a strong understanding of its role in the study.

Expanding the theoretical framework to explicitly discuss how this work advances the understanding of earnings informativeness in high-risk contexts would strengthen the paper. Clarifying the gap in the literature and providing a more robust rationale for the hypotheses would also help the reader appreciate the study’s originality.

Additionally, the inclusion of analyses on conditional conservatism and hidden assets appears disconnected from the stated hypotheses. These analyses aim to explain why losses may have low informativeness, but they are not presented as hypotheses or explicitly tied to the theoretical framework. This lack of alignment creates a sense of methodological inconsistency, making it difficult for the reader to understand how these analyses fit into the overall research objectives. Better integration of these elements into the framework would enhance the coherence and focus of the paper.

3. Methodology and Results

I noticed that the decision to include banks was addressed in a response to a previous reviewer. However, since it is generally common practice to exclude banks, it would be important to clearly explain this choice in the paper. I appreciate the argument provided for their inclusion, as it is well-reasoned. I understand that the methodological approach has already been discussed extensively with other reviewers, and there may be little to add at this stage. That said, presenting the model more clearly in the paper would be highly beneficial. Not all readers will be highly specialized researchers, so ensuring accessibility will help broaden the paper's impact and reach.

4. Conclusion

I encourage the authors to revisit the objectives of their study and provide a concise summary of their key findings and contributions. Clarifying the broader significance of the work and suggesting directions for future research would enhance its impact. A strong final paragraph should highlight the paper's relevance and leave the reader with an inspiring and forward-looking message.

5. Reference

Grant, A. M., & Pollock, T. G. (2011). Publishing in AMJ – Part 3: Setting the Hook. *Academy of Management Journal*, 54(5), 873–879. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amj.2011.4000>